

THE PRESENT TOURISM SERVICES IN SAMARKAND CITY

Shodikulova Mokhigul Ulugbekovna

MA student of Silk Road International

University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

Annotation: This article provides information about services and tourism infrastructure in Samarkand city, and some benefits of future tourism services which serve for raising of flow tourists in Samarkand city.

Key words: *hospitality, historical places, accommodation, services, economical profit.*

Samarkand city very famous with its culture, historical places, history and hospitality to world community. There are deep interesting and colorful history of city that can attract every foreigners. City has great huge touristic potential in current time due to its ancient monuments and culture. Especially, city situated in the center of Great Silk Road and became one of the developed country during Timurids dynasty in XV century. Most of unique buildings also built at that time, and they are playing essential role for developing of tourism industry and brand image of city in present time.

Taking into consideration all opportunities, government paid attention to show tourism treasure of city and several rules were accepted in order to improve all services connected with tourism. The service sector plays an enormously important part in people's lives. It is evolving daily in the global sector as a result. In Uzbekistan, efforts are also being made to develop this industry.

The service sector, which is one of the most emerging areas of the economy, is closely linked to tourism. More tourism would open up opportunities for the organisation of new economic sectors in Uzbekistan. Today in our region the

historical-cultural, pilgrimage, ecological, gastronomic, cultural-educational, archeological, health-improving and agrotourism directions of tourism are rapidly developing, and the number of objects is growing every year. Among Asian countries Uzbekistan has the potential of tourism that showing traditions connected history, becoming a popular travel destination due to its advantageous location and strategic possibilities.

One of the most interesting aspects of Samarkand is its hospitality sector. Going forward, it may increase even higher. The most important strategy to grow tourism is through the various ways that hosts provide their services. Our services may differ in that we provide openness, kindness, and efficient planning. Next, we must provide such services with the appropriate and suitable lodging, dining, and entertainment options for the anticipated number of visitors. People frequently classify their travel destination based on the arrangement of the previously listed components. When travellers visit new locations and take in new amenities, their opinions are influenced by those locations. Furthermore, the ease of access to certain locations greatly affects the number of tourists opinions regarding decisions.

Everytime who travels around city, travelers or tourists may see how hospitality developed in this historical city during their trip. Because, before visit to Uzbekistan foreigners will get all essential information about country and then according to services,accommodation and gastronomy tourism they will decide to come here. Due to this aspects tourism field should be equipped in high level, in order to show high services to visitors . Most travelers visit for visiting to sightseeing places and to discover somewhere or something new for them, while this process foreigners use different services. It includes accommodation (hotels, guesst houses), national cuisine (meals, gastronomy tourism of country), transportation (aircraft, train, taxi services, bus) and different benefits such as shopping, entertainment, asking information from Tourist Information Centers

and others.

Businesses highlight the financial benefits of the tourism industry for a variety of reasons. Organisations in the tourism sector rely heavily on one another as well as on other organisations, the government, and local residents. Financial benefits from the tourism sector will essentially benefit everyone in different ways. The financial implications of the tourism sector are therefore crucial to state, local, and community planning as well as economic development.

Samarkand plays important role on the way enhancing tourism field and that's why essential needs and services should support by government. They are:

1. Advertisement and service (sale) services (growth of itineraries, booking of transport, accommodation).

2. Services of administrative organizing (rent, quarantine, currency, customs, police, as well as visa, passport).

3. Information services (tourist resources in a particular region of the globe, means of residing, customs and border procedures, currency rates in the country of origin, newspapers, magazines, travel guides about the types and directions of transport).

4. Inspections on the protection of historical and cultural places.

5. Travel accommodation (hotels, camping, boarding houses, sanatoriums, tourist bases, etc.).

6. Travel food (restaurants, cafes, bars, etc.)

7. Traveling around the country in different types of passenger transport and taking it from other countries.

8. To meet the practical and scientific interests of tourists (participation in congresses, assemblies, scientific conferences, seminars, fairs and exhibitions, participation in general and special trade events).

9. Trading services of general and special trading enterprises (sale of gifts, cards, etc.)

10. Insurance and medical services

11. Excursion services (translators, groups, tour guides).

12. Services for satisfying cultural interests (visits to theaters, cinemas, concert halls, parks and other nature and sporting events).

A comprehensive analysis of the measures taken to develop tourism in the country, the changing situation on world markets and the increasing competition among the countries of the Great Silk Road require further solutions to a number of problems in the field of ensuring the availability and interconnection of transport services, the competitiveness of tourist infrastructure capable of serving at a high and high quality the level of both external and internal tourists, as well as the recognition of the national tourism brand in the world market.

In addition to huge projects, private business implements projects that do not require much money and time and contribute all their efforts to the development of the industry. Foreign TV channel developers arrived in Samarkand and started working on special programming. One noteworthy development is that Samarkand joined the World Tourism Cities Federation (WTCF) last year. This implies that Samarkand will surely establish itself as one of the world's premier tourist destinations.

References:

1. Zabkar, V., Brencic, M.M. & Dmitrovic, T. (2010). Modelling perceived quality, visitor satisfaction and behavioral intentions at destination level. *Tourism Management* 31(4), 537-546.

2. Chen, C.F. & Tsai, D.C. 2007. How destination image and evaluative factor affect behavioural intentions. *Tourism Management* 28(4). 1115-1122.

3. Abdullayev A., Imansyah A. THE WAYS OF WORD-FORMATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE // Current approaches and new research in modern

sciences. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 5-9.

4. Al-Ababneh, M. (2013). Service quality and its impact on tourist satisfaction. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business* 4(11): 164-176.